

PSYCHOLOGICAL SHIFTS IN UNIVERSITY STUDENTS WHEN THE TARGET LANGUAGE BECOMES THE MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION

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Abstract. The article examines psychological changes in university students when the language being studied becomes a means of instruction. Pedagogical conditions for productive and effective study of a foreign language by students at a university are determined, and aspects of solving this issue are identified.

Keywords: successful learning, productive learning, generalized method, competent approach, student

A huge number of students make efforts to continue their education in the language vertical, starting to study foreign languages in adulthood at a university. This is due to the deep international processes of liberalization of society, expansion of international trade and opportunities for cooperation with foreign partners in the field of economics, politics, culture and growth of tourism. However, it is students who experience increased difficulties in learning a foreign language, which is mainly due to the existing ineffective previous experience of studying a foreign language and high requirements for the duration of study. Hence the need to determine the pedagogical conditions for effective study of a foreign language at a university. A successful solution to this problem is due to at least two aspects:

According to psychologists, with age, logical memory improves compared to mechanical memory, but short-term memory becomes worse. A positive factor is the interconnectedness and coordination of functions, which can compensate for individual deficiencies. For example, developed logical thinking, accumulated experience, the ability to draw conclusions and sums of presented knowledge will help to replenish the volume of short-term memory. Linguistic experience is a set of all knowledge of a linguistic nature, both in the native language and in

foreign languages. Experience can have both a positive and negative impact on the effectiveness of learning. Insufficient vocabulary in the native language, especially in the professional field, will complicate the understanding and successful acquisition of lexical and grammatical constructions. Motivation is of particular importance in teaching students, which is expressed in motivating a person to act, in mobilizing his inner energy, in the direction of his actions and deeds. There is no doubt that teaching students at a university requires a specific organization of the educational process and special forms of pedagogical and andragogical communication. The learner's requirements and demands for the effectiveness of the educational process are very high, and they are caused not only by immediate personal and professional motives, interests and needs, but also by the fact that a specialist is inclined to measure the effectiveness of his professional activity with the effectiveness of the educational process. Working with an adult audience consisting of highly qualified specialists requires attention to the personality of each learner, taking into account his social role in life and society. Properly organized pedagogical communication allows intensifying the educational process and increasing the speech activity of learners. To create optimal conditions for linguistic and psychological comfort in the learning process, one should strive for natural informal communication, which is characterized by friendly participation, emotional responsiveness and attention to the interlocutor. The tone of the address should be extremely benevolent, trusting, interested in students.

One of the factors of intensification in these methods is the principle of communicativeness, which involves creating real communicative activity situations in the classroom, during which the necessary language tools are unintentionally acquired. This predetermined the need to master all types of speech activity: speaking and listening comprehension, as well as reading and writing, and correctly built-in pronunciation. The main task of the method of teaching a foreign language to students is to master a foreign language as a means of communication and a means of cognition under a strict time limit. This requires a minimum of vocabulary and language material in general, which the student must master for his full participation as an individual in the communication process. The selection of vocabulary material for the course of teaching students a language occurs according to the frequency-thematic principle, their semantic value, and compatibility. As for the grammatical phenomena of the language, they are all reflected in the course of study. In working with students, the cognitive-communicative method, that is, teaching

through cognition, comprehension, and understanding of the language system, fully justifies itself. Pure imitation and reproduction can give positive results only at the initial stage. The most fully meet the declared goals such methods. Which are based on a personality-oriented approach. The currently practiced personality-oriented technologies include: learning in cooperation, the project method, the "student portfolio", Internet technologies, that is, we are talking about the formation of a generalized method of mastering foreign language speech activity, which today is called the "competence approach". This means the formation of various competencies: not only the transfer of a certain amount of knowledge, but the formation of an opinion, attitude, as well as the ability and desire to further improve. Which is especially important when teaching adult-students: For the described category of students, knowledge of a foreign language does not seem sufficient for several hours of classroom lessons, while we know that the personal qualities of each of these students formed by a certain age form a special form of perception of foreign language educational material included in the classroom. Effective and comprehensive teaching of a foreign language to students is possible only when adult students independently practice the studied material, making up for the lack of foreign language practice, demonstrating a desire for self-improvement. Due attention should be paid to such interdisciplinary concepts as "attention", "memory" and "thinking", which acquire a specific coloring when teaching adults, because these categories determine the foreign language educational process. Some scientists, considering this concept in pedagogy and methodology of teaching languages, describe it as the ability of students to concentrate on a specific object in the process of studying this object, given that this process is aimed at a more accurate and complete mastery of the material. According to many leading world andrologists, university students have a number of differences from schoolchildren. The main ones are as follows:

In the framework of the methodology of teaching foreign languages, it makes sense to consider language andragogy, which is a section of the methodology aimed at studying various ways of effectively managing the process of formation and development of foreign language communicative competence in university students, and this causes psychological changes when the studied language becomes a means of teaching. Hence the following feature follows, which is that students are able to consciously choose to continue their education at a given age. Psychological and physiological characteristics include self-awareness, self-regulation, self-correction and economic independence, knowledge of rights and laws in society, the formation of a system of morality and ethics. They are also distinguished from younger age groups of students by the presence of experience in everyday, social and professional spheres of life.

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